

IMMUNITY BOOSTER HERBAL PLANTS WITH THEIR USES AND CONSTITUENTS: A REVIEW

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KEYWORDS

Immunomodulators,
herbal, botanical
products,
therapeutic, toxicity

ABSTRACT

Major highlights of this review are on the description about immunomodulators from plant origin with phytochemical compounds and their relevance mechanism of action. Several plants having potential immunomodulatory property have been discussed in this review, several other plants possessing similar type of activities have also been explored as natural immunomodulators. Herbal formulation may be therefore recommended for use as positive immunomodulator. There are several botanical products with potential therapeutic applications because of their efficiency, low cost and low toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

The immune system is extremely important, and its primary goal is to keep us healthy and active. Our immune system will be able to continue fighting viruses, dangerous bacteria, parasites, and toxins if we eat foods that are entirely pure and rich of vitamins, enzymes, and minerals (Maqbool, M. and Ishaq, G, M. 2020). Immune regulation is crucial for the maintenance of immune system homeostasis. (Jantan, I. *et al.*; 2018).

An immunomodulator is a biological or synthetic drug that can stimulate, inhibit, or modify any component of the immune system, including both the innate and adaptive arms. Any alteration in the immune response that involves expression, amplification, or inhibition of any component of the immune response is referred to as immune response modulation. (Das, S. *et al.*; 2014).

Biological products of animals and plants sources have been used by humans for thousands of years either (Khodadadi, S. 2015). The Use of medicinal plants has increased in recent years as a result of their convenience and affordability. (Khumalo.B.M.*etal*;2018)

The abnormalities of immune regulation are involved in many diseases and disorders. (Xiao, C.*etal*;2018). Medicinal plants have long been used to treat a wide range of diseases, including those caused by insects, fungi, bacteria, and viruses, as evidenced by human history. Sharma,P.*et al*;2017)People might use medicinal herbs to strengthen their immunity during health problems. The main cause of death in such situations is a lack of immunity. As a result, it is critical to strengthen our immune system. (Maqbool,M. and Ishaq,G,M . 2020).

Immunomodulation of immune response is now being recognised as a potential alternative to conventional chemotherapy for a number of diseases, particularly when the host's defensive mechanism must be stimulated under situations of decreased immune responsiveness. Recently the clinical potential of six plantderivedanti-inflammatory compounds-curcumin, colchicine, resveratrol, capsaicin, epigallocatechin-3-gallate [EGCG] and quercetin has been highlighted in Furst and Zundorf(2014).

Ayurvedic therapy procedures also include the use of plant components. They are generally non-toxic and have no negative effects. Antiviral and immunity-boosting properties of several sections of medicinal plants are well-known.(Kim, HY.*et al*;2010) Plant extracts, according to Ayurveda, an ancient medicinal science, can do a lot to strengthen the body.(Patil, A. *et al*;2020). Medicinal plants are valuable sources of components that can be employed in the development of pharmacopoeial, non-pharmacopoeial, and synthetic medications. Herbal medicine has numerous advantages, including being easier to obtain than prescription medications, stabilising hormones and metabolism, natural healing, and immune system strength. (Tamboliet *al*, 2021). Herbs are utilised as medicinal basis in a variety of ways by humans throughout their lives. Various herbs have been found to have immune-stimulating characteristics, which can aid in cancer prevention. Phytochemicals such as flavonoids, lignans, terpenoids, carotenoids, and plant sterols have been discovered in many herbs.Several of these phytochemicals are either nitrosation inhibitors or DNA formation inhibitors encourage the production of defensive enzymes. (Khodadadi , S. 2015)

Plants are rich in flavonoids, vitamin C, carotenoids So it can strengthen immune system function. The flavonoid-rich herbs may also possess mild anti - inflammatory action. Many of the plants contain potent antioxidant compounds that supply significant protection against

chronic diseases. (Khodadadi , S. 2015) These compounds may defend LDL cholesterol from oxidation , inhibit cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase enzymes, prevent lipid peroxidation or have antitumour activity .(Gebreyohannes,G.*etal*;2013). Herbal plants have an anti-microbial substance which either kill bacteria, fungi, protozoan etc. or inhibits their growth. (Oraonet *al*;2020)

The use of a variety of agents to enhance immunological and nonspecific host defences and thus to alter it approvingly is an exciting development in immunopharmacology i.e such agents may act by increase the humoral antibody responses, enhancing the phagocytic activity of macrophages or modifying the cell-mediated immune response.(Satoskaret *al*; 2008) Immunomodulatory agents derive from both plant and animal which increases the immune responsiveness of the body against pathogens by activating the non specific immune system. The immune system disorder is responsible for various diseases like allergy, asthma, arthritis, cancer and other infectious diseases. So modulation of immune responses is much required to controlling the various infectious diseases. (Ramesh,P.*et al*;2012)

Plants are the primary source of medications, which have been utilised as herbal remedies for health care, prevention, and cure of many diseases and disorders since ancient times. The majority of plant medicinal actions have been linked to secondary metabolites. (Timothyet *al* ; 2008) .Plant drug discovery requires a multidisciplinary strategy that includes botanical, ethnobotanical, and phytochemical and biological techniques.(Archanaet *al*;2011)

A strong immune system helps the body in fighting flu, disease-causing viruses, and bacteria. People with weakened immune systems are more likely to become ill, and their symptoms are more severe than those of others. That is why having a strong immune system is critical because it allows us to live a healthy life. (Singh, S .2020)

Around 122 chemicals derived from plants have been identified as therapeutic substances that are also used in commercial drugs; for example, the bark of the willow tree is high in salicylic acid, which is also an active metabolite of aspirin, and this bark has been used as a pain reliever and antipyretic substance since ancient times. Some of the drugs which are frequently used by the physicians are also derived from plant sources, for example, aspirin, digoxin, quinine and opium, etc.(Dias,DA *etal*;2012) They have a long history of use as herbal drug. Currently, there is much growing interest to use these medicinal plants as modulators of the complex immune system.(Sharma,P.*et al*;2017, Mehmood,Z. *et al*;2018)

The aim of this study is to document the medicinal plants species used by herbalists to boost the immune system of people. This review article gives an overall view about some natural herbs like *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulsi), *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi , Gilloy), *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) , *Allium sativum* (Garlic) , *Gingiber officinale* (Ginger) , *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha) , *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric) , *Piper nigrum* (Black Peeper), *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) , *Nigella sativa* (Black cumin), *Panax quinquefolius* (American Ginseng) , *Astragalus membranaceus* (Astragalus), *Cinnamomum cassia* (Cinnamon) , *Emblica officinalis* (Amla).

Review of Literature:

More than 80% of people, primarily in South Asia and Europe, use herbal medicines for their primary health care, according to the World Health Organization. According to studies, they have anti-inflammatory qualities in addition to strengthening immunity. Herbal remedies have been employed in phytoproducts, bee products, and other products since ancient times. (Singh, S. 2020).

Due to a growing awareness of immune system modulation and to bring about the desired effects on disease prevention, the immunomodulating capabilities of plants have been investigated extensively with greater interest in recent years. Various plant medicines used in traditional medicine make advantage of their anti-infective qualities not only by directly impacting the pathogen but also by indirectly impacting the pathogen. (Shukla ,S.*et al*; 2012)

Ethnobotany is the study of indigenous plants for their medical characteristics, and it's a good way to find new medications in the future. More than 300 plants have been recognised as having medicinal potential, according to data from 2015-16. Current research into developing plant-derived natural compounds as effective and safer leads to function as immunomodulators is attracting a lot of attention. (Sharma, P.*et al*;2017).

In India, there are over 20,000 medicinal plants. Almost 800 plants are utilized in the treatment of various ailments. There are around 4000 phytochemicals identified, of which 150 have been investigated in depth and categorised based on physical, chemical, and defensive activities. (Harichandan, *et al*;2019).

Plants are used by a huge population in India for their healing, preventative, curative, and therapeutic properties, as well as immunostimulatory properties.(Archana, *et al*; 2011).

By re-establishing physiological homeostasis, several therapeutic plants promote positive health and sustain organic resistance to illness. Many polysaccharides extracted from higher plants are thought to be biological response modifiers, enhancing immunological responses such as complement activation, lymphocyte proliferation, and macrophage stimulation. Flavonoids are found in plants. (Savant, C. *et al*;2014)

2.1 Immunomodulation by Medicinal Plants:

The chemoprotective and immunomodulatory properties of plant extracts used in conventional medicine are being investigated. Immunomodulators are biological response modifiers that work against tumours by enhancing the host's defence mechanisms. They have a direct anti-proliferative effect on tumour cells and also improve the host's ability to resist hazardous chemical harm.

Immunomodulatory therapy may be a viable alternative to traditional chemotherapy for a variety of diseases, particularly when the host's defence mechanisms must be activated in the face of impaired immune responsiveness or when selective immunosuppression is required in situations such as inflammatory diseases, auto-immune disorders, or organ/bone marrow transplantation. A number of Indian medicinal plants and various 'Rasayana' have been claimed to possess immunomodulatory activity. Some of these plants are *Withania somnifera*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, and *Mangifera indica*. A lot more are still to be explored and offer scope for further investigation. (Singh, N. *et al*;2016)

2.2 How medicinal plants can help immune system?

Plants that are high in flavonoids, vitamin C, or carotenoids can help to boost immunity. Flavonoid-rich plants may also have anti-inflammatory properties. Their positive effects have been labelled as anti-inflammatory and immune-stimulant. (Khodadadi, S. *et al*;2015). It has the ability to stimulate lymphocyte activity, phagocytosis, and interferon production. Garlic, for example, is one of the most fascinating herbs that has a significant impact on the immune system. Garlic, as an immune system booster, has been discovered to stimulate natural killer cell activity, which has an immunological-potentiating impact. Garlic, for example, has a higher concentration of sulphur combinations, which are responsible for its medicinal effects, and some studies strongly imply that it is a good option as an immunological modulator, preserving immune function homeostasis. Garlic's chemical components have also been discovered to be effective in the treatment of cancer, diabetes, atherosclerosis, and hyperlipidemia. (Gebreyohannes, G. *et al*;2013).

2.3 Anticancer activity of herbs:

Many herbs contain phyosterols, saponins, flavonoids, triterpenes, and carotenoids, which have been proven to be cancer chemo-protective in studies of legumes, fruit, and vegetables. These beneficial compounds act as antioxidants and electrophile hunters, as well as stimulating the immune system, inhibiting hormonal actions and metabolic pathways linked to cancer development, inhibiting nitrosation and the formation of DNA adducts with carcinogens, and inducing phase I or II detoxification enzymes. (Salminen, A.*et al*;2008).

In the world, there has been a dramatic increase in awareness of the usage of herbal products. Herbal use has been found to be common in cancer patients, ranging from 13 percent to 63 percent in some studies. Aside from the limited therapeutic range associated with most anticancer drugs. The National Cancer Institute has identified some commonly used herbs as having cancer-preventive effects. These herbs are members of the Allium family like garlic, members of the Labiatae (mint) family, members of the Zingiberaceae family like ginger and members of the Umbelliferae (carrotfamily).(Gebreyohannes, G.*et al*;2013).

Terpenoids act as a chemical defence against environmental stress and as a healing process in plants. Traditional medicines are frequently used to treat cancer and inflammatory illnesses. As a result, conventional medicine defends findings that show plant-derived terpenoid components can inhibit the key regulator (nuclear factor-B signalling) in the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases and cancer. (Salminen, A.*et al*;2008).

2.4 Herbal Plants as Immunomodulator:

Several Herbs have potent immunomodulatory action. For example- *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (tulsi) ,*Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi , Gilloy) ,*Azadirachta indica* (Neem) ,*Allium sativum* (Garlic) ,*Gingiber officinale* (Ginger) ,*Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha) ,*Curcuma longa*(Turmeric),*Piper nigrum* (Black Peeper),*Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) , *Nigella sativa* (Black cumin), *Panax quinquefolius* (American Ginseng) , *Astragalus membranaceus* (Astragalus) , *Cinnamomum cassia* (Cinnamon) ,*Embllica officinalis* (Amla).

2.4.1 *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulsi) :

Family: Lamiaceae Common Names: Holy basil, Tulsi.

Ocimum tenuiflorum Linn is known by several names in Ayurveda, including "Queen of Herbs," "The Incomparable One," "Mother Medicine of Nature," and so on. Tulsi, according

to Ayurvedic tradition, is a tonic for the mind, body, and spirit that can help with a variety of modern-day ailments. (Khurana, p; 2020). *Ocimum tenuiflorum* Linn are mostly grown from seeds and vegetative proliferation. Various helpful items for example- essential oils, herbal tea, wood are obtained from this medicinal plant. (Gupta, P; 2020)

Chemical Constituents: Some main chemical constituents of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* Linn which are present in the major amount are:- Oleanolic Acid, Ursolic Acid, Rosmarinic Acid, Eugenol, Carvacrol, Linalool, Beta-Caryophyllene, Estragole Methyl Cinnamate. Essential oil consists mostly of Eugenol (~70%), Beta-Elementene (~11%), & Beta-Caryophyllene (~8%), Germacrene (~2%)

Role in Immunity: Tulsi plays an important function in enhancing the immune system, which helps the human body fight off undesirable microbial invaders such as germs and viruses (Srivastava, A.K. et al; 2020). Tulsi is well known for its medicinal properties like antibacterial, antifungal, antipyretic, antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, apitizer. (Singh, R. K, 2019). Various elements of the plant are said to be effective in treating a variety of ailments. Tulsi has been shown to improve respiratory parameters and aid in the recovery from asthma attacks. Tulsi plays an important role in boosting the immune system, which helps the human body fight off unwanted microbial strangers such as bacteria and viruses. (Srivastava, A.K. et al; 2020). *O. sanctum* seed oil provided a considerable rise in anti-SRBC antibody titre and a considerable suppression of antigen-induced histamine release from peritoneal mast cells in non-stressed mice. (Mukherjee, P.K et al, 2014).

2.4.2 *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi Or Gilloy):

Family: Menispermaceae

Common Names :Guduchi, Gilloy, Amrita, Heart leaved moonseed, Gulbel.

Tinospora cordifolia (guduchi or giloy) is a tropical Indian subcontinent herbaceous vine belonging to the Menispermaceae family. The heart-shaped leaves and reddish berries give it the name **heart-leaved moonseed**. It is regarded as one of the best Rasayanas and is notable for its remarkable flexibility. (Srivastava, A.K. et al; 2020). The wood is white, delicate, and porous, and it rapidly takes on a yellow hue when freshly cut. (Chaudhary, V; 2020)

Chemical Constituents: *T. cordifolia* extract contains many biologically important phytochemicals including lactones, alkaloids, glycosides, steroids, sesquiterpenoid,

diterpenoid, aliphatic compounds, phenolics, polysaccharides and flavonoid which play immunomodulatory activity in human body.(Singh , G *et al*;2017)

Role in immunity: Gilloy has anti-diabetic , antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory , antiperiodic, antispasmodic, anti-arthritis, anti-allergic , antimicrobial, anti-osteoporotic and immune modulatory properties . Its antioxidant potentials were also investigated in many studies .Methanol extract of Gilloy is found to have broad spectrum antimicrobial effectiveness against various strains which are Staphylococcus aureus, Klebsiella pneumonia, Escherichia coli, Shigella flexneri, Salmonella paratyphi, Salmonella typhimurium, Salmonella typhi, and Proteus vulgaris.(Saha ,*Setal*;2012) Due to its alkaloid components including tinosporin, tetrahydropalmatine, choline, palmatine and magnoflorine, it also has protective role against aflatoxininduced nephrotoxicity. With their broad beneficial activity, it plays important role to improve our immune system to fight against infectious diseases. (More,p and Pai K; 2011,Aher V.D, Wahi A.K;2010, Kalikar Mv,*et al*;2008)**T. cordifolia** extract showed an antitumor potential against the skin carcinogenesis in a mouse model (Chaudhary, R *etal*;2008)

2.4.3Azadirachtaindica (Neem):

Family: Meliaceae Common Names : Neem , Indian lilac.

The tree *Azadirachta indica*, commonly known as neem, grows to a height of 12-18 metres with a straight branch. It is mostly found in India's northern regions. It is evergreen, but during periods of extreme dryness, it may lose most or all of its leaves. The branches are long and spreading.(Uzzaman,S; 2019).Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seeds contain a large amount of oil that has medical and botanical properties.(Maithani ,A .*etal*;2011)

Chemical Constituents: The main components of neem include quercetin, azadirachtin, and nimbosterol, which are found in various areas of the plant. In addition, the leaves contain a variety of chemicals such as nimbanene, 6 – desacetylnimbinene, nimboldid, and several types of amino acids. (Husain Rahmani, A *et al*; 2018)

The leave part consist of a chemical constituent like quercetin and the oil of *Azadirachta indica* contains nimbin and nimbidine. The bark part contains tannins, gallic acid, diterpenoids are active against klebsiella and staphylococcus species.(Maithani, A *et al*;2011)

Role in Immunity: *Azadirachta indica* has anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, antibacterial, antifungal, immunomodulatory ,wound healing effect, anti microbial, hepatoprotective effect, antidiabetic activity, anti-nephrotoxicity effect, neuroprotective effects, anti-cancerous

properties and neem tree effectively works in air purifying (Maragathavalli, S., Brindha, *etal*;2012).Gayathri R Menon et al. (2016) conducted a study to investigate the antibacterial activity of neem oil using a bacterial pathogen. Nimbidin is a tetranortriterpene combination found in the seed oil of *A. indica* that has powerful anti-inflammatory and antiarthritic properties. The chloroform extracts of *A. indica* and the aqueous, methanolic extracts of *B. spectabilis* demonstrated good oral glucose tolerance and dramatically reduced intestinal glucosidase activity. After 21 days of treatment, *A. indica* chloroform and *B. spectabilis* aqueous extracts increased glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity and hepatic and skeletal muscle glycogen content significantly. (Bhat, M *etal*;2011)

2.4.4 *Allium sativum* (Garlic):

Family: Alliaceae Common Names : Garlic

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.; Family: Amaryllidaceae) is a fragrant herbaceous annual spice that has been used as traditional medicine from ancient times. (Badalet *al*;2019). It is considered the second broadly used *Allium* species with onion (*Allium cepa* L.), which is used as a remedy against several common diseases such as cold, influenza, snake bites, and hypertension. (Barnes, J *et al*;2002) **Garlic** has long been used in cooking as a spice to flavour items while they are being prepared. It also has medicinal uses, such as treating lung illnesses, whooping cough, stomach disorders, colds, and earaches, as well as assisting in the prevention of cardiovascular disease. (Badalet *al*;2019)

Chemical Constituents: Sulphur-based compounds such as diallyl polysulfides, vinyl dithiin, ajoene, S-allyl cysteine, alliin, and a few non-sulphur compounds such as enzymes, saponins, maillard reaction products, and flavonoids constitute the majority of the chemical constituents of garlic, which are responsible for its distinct smell and taste. The primary odoriferous compounds in freshly milled garlic homogenates are S-propyl-cysteine-sulfoxide (PCSO), allicin, and S-methyl cysteine-sulfoxide (MCSO). (Zeng, Y *et al*;2017)

Role In Immunity: Garlic and its associated chemicals have long been thought to offer a variety of biological properties, including anticarcinogenic and antioxidant properties, antidiabetic, renoprotective, anti-atherosclerotic, antibacterial, antifungal and antihypertensive activities (Badal, D.S *et al*;2019). Garlic has been proposed as a promising candidate for preserving immune system balance. Because allicin is unstable, it gradually degrades into sulphur-containing molecules with therapeutic effects. When white blood cells in the body come into contact with viruses, such as those that cause the common cold or flu, these

chemicals have been found to increase their disease-fighting response. Fructans (fructoligosaccharides) found in aged garlic extract selectively stimulate some beneficial bacteria in the colon, regulating immunological responses. (Chandrashekar PM, et al, 2017)

2.4.5 *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger):

Family: Zingiberaceae Common Name: Ginger.

Zingiber officinale commonly called ginger belongs to the family Zingiberaceae. Plants in the Zingiberaceae family feature tuberous or non-tuberous rhizomes, each with its own distinct fragrance and medicinal characteristics. (Supreetha S, et al; 2011). In the traditional medicine, thick underground stem (rhizome) of ginger is commonly used.

Chemical Constituents: Essential oils, phenols, oleoresins, proteolytic enzymes, and other vitamins and minerals are among the active ingredients in Ginger root. Zingiberene, zingiberole, camphene, Cineole, bisabolene, phellandrene, citral, borneol, citronellol, geraniol, linalool, limonene, and camphene are all major components of ginger essential oils. Phenols include gingerol and zingerone while gingerol and shogaol included among oleoresins. Other active constituents are mucilages, proteins, vitamin B6, vitamin C, calcium magnesium, phosphorus, potassium, sulfur and linoleic acid. (Poeloengan M; 2011)

Role In Immunity: Ginger is used in Ayurvedic and herbal medicine for a long period. Ginger's medicinal, chemical, and pharmacological qualities, as well as evidence for its usage as an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory agent, antinausea substance, and anticancer agent, as well as its preventive effect against other sickness conditions, have all been thoroughly investigated. Ketones, particularly gingerols, which appear to be the main component of ginger, are present, is responsible for its spicy aroma. (Mashhadi, N.S; 2013). The anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of ginger are due to the gingerols, paradols, sesquiterpenes, shogaols, and zingerone. These compounds exhibit antibacterial properties against a wide range of bacteria, viruses, and fungi. The presence of one of the antioxidant compounds in ginger root, in particular, has potential anti-inflammatory and immune-boosting properties, which helps in enhancing normal metabolic activities in the human body, fighting infections and toxins, and shielding against harmful effects of bacteria, viruses, and other microorganisms. Thus, the Ginger has proved to be a powerful immune booster plant with especial antiviral properties. (Pradhan, LD. et al ; 2013) Fresh ginger, as opposed to dried ginger, has been shown to reduce human respiratory syncytial virus (HRSV)-induced plaque formation in both A549

(adenocarcinomic human alveolar) and HEp-2 (human laryngeal carcinoma) cell lines when given in appropriate amounts.

2.4.6 *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha):

Family: Solanaceae

Common Names : Ashwagandha , Indian ginseng , poison Gooseberry, Winter cherry.

Ashwagandha is a perennial woody shrub that grows to be about 2 feet tall and can be found in a range of ways, including Africa, the Mediterranean, and India. The flowers are little and green, with a smooth, oblong, and spherical orange-red berry as the ripe fruit. It is used for medicinal purposes and has tuberous roots that are more or less brown in colour. The seeds are yellow in colour. (Mir Ahmad, B *et al*;2012).

Constituents: Withanolides, which comprise triterpenelactones-withanolides, withaferin A & D, steroidal lactones, alkaloids, tropine, and cuscohygrine, are the primary chemical elements of ashwagandha. These anolides are bioactive chemicals that have anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties due to their ability to inhibit cyclo-oxygenase-2.(Ryu, YB *et al*;2010)

Role In Immunity: The root of ashwagandha is regarded as tonic, aphrodisiac, narcotic, diuretic, anthelmintic, astringent, thermogenic and stimulant. (Singh, N *et al* ;2011) . According to research, withanolides, ashwagandha's main ingredient, is responsible for the herb's antibacterial, anticancer, and immunomodulating activities. The antioxidants in ashwagandha are important for its immune system strengthening properties. (Hosny Mansour H and Farouk Hafez H. ,2012, Iuvone .T. *et al* 2003) . Ashwagandha also reduces the amount of C-reactive protein in the body, which helps to reduce inflammation (Deshpande .A. *et al* 2017). In human investigations, ashwagandha was found to help boost the number of natural killer cells.

2.4.7 *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric):

Family : Zingiberaceae Common names :Turmeric , yellow ginger , Safflower.

Curcuma longa also known as Turmeric is a perennial herb and belongs to the family Zingiberaceae . Turmeric is a Pungent Asian spice with a fascinating heritage. The “Indian saffron,” (*Curcuma longa*), is a golden orange spice and medicinal herb that has been utilised for thousands of years. It is one of the most extensively examined spices, with therapeutic benefits being investigated

Constituents: Carbohydrates, protein, fat, dietary fibre, minerals, essential oils, and curcuminoids make up the majority of turmeric powder. Curcumin, demethoxycurcumin, and bisdemethoxycurcumin are the most important phytochemicals of Turmeric . (ChaurasiaJP , 2001). The germacrone, turmerone, atlantone and zingiberene are the group of major essential oils which are present in turmeric.

Roles In Immunity: The rhizome, or root, of the turmeric plant is used medicinally, as a flavouring in many dishes, and as a treatment to treat a variety of disorders due to its anti-inflammatory effects. Previous research has shown that it possesses antifungal, antiviral, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and other pharmacological activity therapeutic potential. (Ghosh. S, *et al* ; 2015) . Turmeric's main ingredient, curcumin, has been shown to be responsible for its clinical medicinal benefits. Curcumin also plays an important role in immune system modulation. Turmeric has been studied for its prebiotic-like qualities, which allow it to alter the intestinal bacteria and support the gut-immune relationship. (Peterson . C T ,*et al* 2018). Curcumin has the ability to reduce cortisol levels, which helps to keep the immune system in check. It's significant because cortisol receptors are found on all immune cells, and changes in cortisol levels affect immunological responses. (Adam . EK, 2017).

2.4.8Piper nigrum :

Family: Piperaceae Common names :Black Peeper , Kali Mirch.

Piper nigrum(Peeper) belongs to family Piperaceae and is also known as the "King of Spices" because of its intense aroma. Many tropical countries, such as Brazil, Indonesia, and India, grow black pepper. Piper nigrum has bioactive chemicals that are utilised in medicine, preservatives, and fragrance. It referred as king of spices also due to the extensive use of its dried unripe fruit in almost all cooking worldwide. (Joshi. DR ,*et al*; 2018).

Constituents: This plant contains around 600 different phytochemicals, such as lignans, alkaloids/amides, terpenes, and neolignans, all of which have diverse biological and therapeutic effects. Piperine, a potent alkaloid found in black pepper, is frequently employed in traditional medicine (Ayurveda, Siddha).It contains the major pungent alkaloid piperine (1peperoyl piperidine), which has a number of interesting pharmacological properties, including antihypertensive, antiAlzheimer's, antidepressant, antiplatelet, antiinflammatory, antioxidant, antipyretic, antitumor, antiasthmatic, analgesic, antimicrobial, and so on. (Tiwari, Mahadik, & Gabhe, 2020; Yoo*et al.*, 2019).

Roles In Immunity: When black pepper was introduced, various bacterium kinds flourished, according to a research. Black pepper was found to have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, and fever-reducing qualities, as well as immune system strengthening capabilities. (Maqbool, Mudasir, 2020). Among the many positive biological effects of peppercorn and different secondary metabolites of *Piper nigrum* include antiviral, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, anti-oxidative, anti-thyroid, anticancer, immunological, and vaccine bioavailability increasing properties. Ahmed *et al.*, 2012 evaluated the biological role of black pepper in great detail and style.

2.4.9 *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) :

Family :Myrtaceae

Common Names: Laung , Clove.

Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), a member of the Myrtaceae family, is used as an antiseptic against communicable diseases all over the world due to its antibacterial properties against oral germs. Clove is often utilised in the food business to extend shelf life because to its antibacterial properties. Clove buds, clove oil, eugenol, and oleoresins have been found to be safe as a food supplement by the FDA. (Vijayasteltaret *al* ; 2016).

Constituents: Carbohydrates, protein, vitamins (A, C, E, and K), thiamin, riboflavin, folate, niacin, dietary fibres, and minerals abound in this plant. It also contains phenolic components such as eugenol, thymol, eugenol acetate, and gallic acid, as well as -cariophyllene, which have a wide range of cosmetic, medicinal, food, and agricultural applications. (Gulcin .I, *et al* ;2012)The main bioactive component of clove is eugenol.

Roles In Immunity:

Clove possesses anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, antiviral, antifungal, antibacterial, and antiviral properties (Saleem .HN ,*et al*; 2019) It is also reported the inhibition of Dengue Virus Protease by Eugenin, Isobiflorin, and Biflorin isolated from the Flower Buds of Cloves (Wang. L, *et al* ;2020).

2.4.10 *Nigella sativa* (Black cumin) :

Family: Ranunculaceae Common Names: Black seed , Kalonji , Roman coriander , Black cumin.

Nigella sativa (*N. sativa*) (Family Ranunculaceae) is a popular therapeutic herb in many parts of the world. It is widely used in traditional medical systems such as Unani and Tibb, Ayurveda, and Siddha. Seeds and oil have a long history of traditional use in many medicinal and nutritional systems. The seeds of *N. sativa* have long been used to treat a variety of illnesses and disorders. *N. sativa* is an annual blooming plant that grows to a height of 20-90 cm and has finely split leaves with narrowly linear to threadlike leaf segments. (Ahmad . A ,*et al* ; 2013).

Constituents: So far, many active chemicals have been isolated, identified, and published in various black seed types. Thymoquinone (30% -48%), thymohydroquinone, dithymoquinone, p-cymene (7% -15%), carvacrol (6% -12%), 4-terpineol (2% -7%), t-anethol (1% -4%), sesquiterpene longifolene (1% -8%), -pinene, and thymol are the most important active chemicals. In addition to the substances found in black seeds, there are a few others. Isoquinoline alkaloids, such as nigellicimine and nigellicimine-N-oxide, and pyrazol alkaloids, or indazole ring containing alkaloids, such as nigellidine and nigellicine, are found in seeds. Furthermore, the seeds of *N. sativa* contain alpha-hederin, a water-soluble pentacyclic triterpene, as well as saponin, a possible anticancer agent..(Al-Jassir MS ;1992).

Roles In Immunity: Jaundice, conjunctivitis, rheumatism, diabetes, anorexia, gastrointestinal issues, internal haemorrhage, asthma, cough, bronchitis, fever, bronchitis, influenza, and other health problems have all been reported to be cured by *Nigella sativa*. (. Forouzanfar. F ,*et al* ; 2014) . The principal active phytochemical in black cumin is thymoquinone, which is responsible for the majority of its medicinal benefits. In terms of antiviral activities, *Nigella sativa* oil and seeds have been shown to have viricidal properties against a variety of dangerous viruses, including the hepatitis C virus (HCV) and HIV.(Molla S, *et al* ; 2019)

2.4.11 *Panax quinquefolius* (American Ginseng) :

Family: Araliaceae

Common Names :Ninjin, Pannag, Panax.

Panax ginseng, a member of the Araliaceae family, is mostly found in North America and Asia, and has long been prized for its numerous therapeutic properties. Ginseng is the dried root of *Panax ginseng* (Korean), *Panax japonica* (Japanese), *Panax notoginseng* (Chinese), and *Panax quinquefolium* (Korean) (American). Although active chemicals are present in the root, it is used medicinally.(Gopalkrishnan V *et al.* 2002).

Constituents: Triterpenoid, protopanaxadiols, protopanaxatriols, and steroidal saponins, also known as ginsenosides, polysaccharides, and proteins are the main chemical components of ginseng, and they are responsible for their antibacterial and antiviral properties, particularly against pathogens that cause respiratory infections in humans. Amino acids, alkaloids, phenols, proteins, polypeptides, and vitamins B1 and B2 are among the active substances present in all parts of the plant. (Chadwick DJ, Marsh J; 1997).

Roles In Immunity: Antimicrobial, antioxidative, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, anticholesterol disease, and anticancer characteristics are all present in it. It aids in the improvement of immunity, as well as the treatment of numerous cardiovascular diseases, neurological problems, and diabetes. It has been discovered to be effective against a variety of human viral infections, including rhinovirus, human immunodeficiency virus, influenza virus, hepatitis virus, norovirus, enterovirus, human herpes virus, rotavirus, and coxsackievirus respiratory syncytial virus (Iqbal H, Rhee DK; 2020). Ginseng also suppresses the production of mature biofilms by inhibiting microbial movement and impacts on biofilm formation (Lee J ;2014).

2.4.12 *Astragalus membranaceus* (Astragalus):

Family : Leguminosae. Common Names : Milk-vetchroot, Ogi.

It's made from the dried roots of *Astragalus membranaceus* plants that are 4-7 years old. One of the most important “Qi tonifying” adaptogenic herbs from the Chinese materia medica is *Astragalus membranaceus* (Latin); membranous milk-vetch root (English), huang qi (Chinese), ogi (Japanese), and hwanggi (Korean). (Boswell. A ; 2006)

Constituents: Polysaccharides, saponins, flavonoids, amino acids, and trace elements are the primary components of *Astragalus membranaceus*. Polysaccharides in *Astragalus* that contain mannose, D-glucose, xylose, and Larbinose have been discovered to have anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, and antiviral activities.(Ghasemian-Yadegari J, *et al* ; 2019)

Roles In Immunity: According to studies, *Astragalus* root activates the immune system in a variety of ways. According to one study, *Astragalus* root helps in the promotion and maintenance of respiratory health. *Astragalus* roots are utilised in a variety of Indian and Chinese ayurvedic remedies that assist to improve the immune system and combat ailments. This herb is also popular as natural supplement that assist in combating stress, killing tumor

cells and remedying the chemotherapy symptoms. .(Ghasemian-Yadegari J, *et al* ; 2019). Astragalus polysaccharides were found to boost immunity.(Kallon S, *et al* ; 2013) .

2.4.13 *Cinnamomum cassia*_(Cinnamon) :

Family :Lauraceae Common Names :Chinese cinnamon, Chinese cassia

The Lauraceae family's *Cinnamomum cassia* is a fragrant tree species. Cinnamon has long been a popular ingredient in traditional Chinese, Indian, Persian, and Unani medicine. For thousands of years, cinnamon has been utilised as a popular spice in various places around the world. Cinnamon is made from the bark of young trees and is widely used as a spice all over the world as a daily condiment.

Constituents: A part from significant concentrations of many nutrients such as carbohydrates, proteins, choline, vitamins (A, K, C, B3), and minerals, the oil extract contains a number of biologically active chemicals. According to Ojagh, Rezaei, Razavi, and Hosseini (2012), cinnamon bark includes 21 chemical components, including cinnamaldehyde (60.41 percent) and eugenol (3.19 percent), all of which have antimicrobial properties.

Roles In Immunity : Cinnamon has a significant economic value and can be utilised as a material for medicinal items. Flatulence, amenorrhea, diarrhoea, toothache, fever, leukorrhea, common cold, and headache are among the ailments for which it is prescribed. Cinnamon has also been shown to prevent throat infections when used regularly. (Hajimonfarednejadet *al.*, 2018). Several scientific studies have shown the antimicrobial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, antitumor, gastroprotective, and immunomodulatory effects of cinnamon (Shen *et al.*, 2012).

2.4.14 *Emblica officinalis*_(Amla) :

Family :Euphorbiaceae Common Name: Indian Gooseberry , Amla.

Phyllanthus emblica L. (Synonym: *Emblica officinalis*) is a medium-sized deciduous tree in the Euphorbiaceae family, often known as Indian gooseberry. It is a medicinal plant with significant basic and therapeutic value. Different components of *E. officinalis* are useful for treating various disorders, but the fruits in particular have a wide range of pharmacological and therapeutic uses. (Khurana S, *et al*;2019).

Constituents: Polyphenols, ellagic acid, gallic acid, chebulagic acid, apeigenin, quercetin, corilagin, and leutolin are among the bioactive substances found in the fruit. Fruit pulp contains

sugar-substituted phenolics (flavone, phenolic, flavonol glycosides) and tannins (emblicanin A and B, phyllaemblicin B, punigluconoin). (Variya, B.C. *et al* 2016 and Yadav, S.S. *et al* 2017). Amla extracts have been extensively investigated for different biological activities. These phytochemicals contribute to the antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral and other pharmacological activities.

Roles in Immunity: It promotes in the detoxification of the complete organ system, resulting in improved health and immunity. Amla fruits are said to have a lot of vitamin C in them (Ascorbic acid). It's also high in polyphenols, which are proven to inhibit the growth of cancer cells. Not only that, but there's more. Amla can also help with diabetic management and cholesterol reduction. (Variya, B.C. *et al*;2016). Amla fruit powder enhances to control high blood pressure.

Triphala comprises three herbs namely Amla, harada and bihara. The blood sugar level may be increased by the action of an enzyme alanine transaminase which is present in liver. This enzyme can be normalized by taken one teaspoonful of this mixture (equal quantities of Amla, jamun and bitter gourd powder) once or twice per day. Chromium, a mineral present in Amla fruits responsible for the anti-diabetic effect .(Devarajala S. *et al*; 2011).

Conclusion

Plants are one of the most important sources of medicines. Medicinal Plants are rich in secondary metabolites which are potential sources of drugs and of therapeutic importance and has also attained a significant role in health system all over the world for both humans and animals not only in diseased condition but also as a potential material for maintaining proper health. Major highlights of this review are on the description about immunomodulators from plant origin with phytochemical compounds and their relevance mechanism of action. Several plants having potential immunomodulatory property have been discussed in this review, several other plants possessing similar type of activities have also been explored as natural immunomodulators. Herbal formulation may be therefore recommended for use as positive immunomodulator. There are several botanical products with potential therapeutic applications because of their efficiency, low cost and low toxicity.

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